

DEVELOPING MIXER-STYLE CONTROLLERS BASED ON ARDUINO / TEENSY MICROCONTROLLERS

Dr. Constantin Popp

constantin@knobtronix.co.uk

MSc Eng. Rosalia Soria-Luz

rosalia@knobtronix.co.uk

ABSTRACT

Low-cost MIDI mixer-style controllers may not lend themselves to the performance practice of electroacoustic music. This is due to the limited bit depth in which values of controls are transmitted and potentially the size and layouts of control elements, providing only coarse control of sound processes running on a computer. As professional controllers with higher resolution and higher quality controls are more costly and possibly rely on proprietary protocols, the paper investigates the development process of custom DIY controllers based on the Arduino and Teensy 3.1 micro controllers, and Open Source software. In particular, the paper discusses the challenges of building higher resolution controllers on a restricted budget with regard to component selection, printed circuit board and enclosure design. The solutions, compromises and outcomes are presented and analysed in fader-based and knob-based prototypes.

1. INTRODUCTION

In their performance practise the authors use mixer-style controllers to diffuse and improvise electroacoustic music, in particular the Korg nanoKONTROL [1] and a Behringer BCF2000 [2]. The two controllers are readily available and immediately compatible with computer music software, as they are relying on the MIDI protocol for data transfer. Although both provide plenty controls to adjust sound processes running in the computer, they transmit the controls in 7 bit and therefore may not lend themselves to nuanced control. Furthermore, the nanoKONTROL also compromises tactility for compactness with it's short 45 mm faders and small hard-touch knobs (Figure 1).

Other controllers, such as the Mackie Control Universal Pro XT [3] may be more touch friendly and would offer higher resolution but they are in comparison expensive (starting around 700 pounds) and the used protocols are closed source / proprietary.

While others have investigated the departure from a mixer-style controller using, among others, accelerometers [4], capacitive touch [5] or optical sensors [6], the authors sought for an incremental improvement, focusing mainly on improving the resolution and layout of the controller with respect to the nanoKONTROL and the BCF2000. To solve

Figure 1. Size comparison of a Korg nanoKONTROL with a Behringer BCF2000 and 10 British pence.

these issues, the authors decided to develop their own mixer-style controllers.

2. GENERAL DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

2.1 Choosing a platform

Because of the accessibility and wide-spread use of the Arduino platform, the Teensy 3.1 from PJRC [7] and the Sparkfun Pro Micro [8] were chosen. Both are only around 35.56 mm by 17.78 mm small and can be programmed using the Arduino IDE. The community around the Arduino developed already Open Source software libraries for USB-MIDI [9], OSC [10] and network communication [11], solving the need to deal with communication protocols manually.

2.2 Hardware and software considerations

The authors sought for a scalable hard- and software solution accommodating a variable number of knobs, faders and switches. That suggested the use of sixteen channel analog multiplexers (Texas Instruments CD74HC4067E) for reading the voltages of analog potentiometers and eight channel digital multiplexers (Texas Instruments SN74HC138N and SN74HC151N) for reading and setting the state of switches and LEDs, reducing the need of a high number of input and output pins on the microcontroller. The microcontroller then connects to the computer via USB and draws the necessary power from it. Figure 2 shows a schematic diagram

3. CHALLENGES

With regard to the hardware and enclosure, several aspects made the development complicated.

3.1 Hardware

Firstly, we relied on online shopping for finding and purchasing parts. To determine if a part suits the requirements it needs to be bought and tested in case it's datasheet sounds promising. This was especially problematic for finding the desired combination of knobs and potentiometers as not every knob fits every potentiometer and not every knob feels touch friendly. In the end 9 mm ALPS potentiometer with a 6 mm D shaft were chosen and paired with Multicomp soft touch knobs (CR-BA-7C6-180D) (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Schematic overview of the hardware design.

of the hardware implementation. The software side deals with signal conditioning, I/O management (controlling the multiplexers, sending and receiving data via USB-MIDI, ADC conversion) and controller configuration.

Capturing and transmitting values of the knobs and faders with more than 7 bit affects the hard- and software design. The Arduino offers analog to digital conversion in 10 bit resolution, whereas the Teensy 3.1 up to 13 bit. The authors decided to transmit the captured values to the computer using the MIDI protocol. Two consecutive control change messages transmit the 10 bit (11 bit in case of the Teensy 3.1) values with the higher bits arriving first, the lower bits last. That way, the convenience of MIDI could be used, relieving the need to use OSC just out of consideration of bit depth. Alternative ways to transmit the data could be implemented as the firmware is Open Source.

The development of initial prototypes – a knobbox and a faderbox – was straight forward (Figure 3). However, making the prototypes more usable and reliable opened up new challenges.

Figure 3. Initial prototypes of the knobbox (top) and faderbox (bottom).

Figure 4. Size comparison of the potentiometer (1), 10 British pence (2), the CR-BA-7C6-180D (3) and the knob of a nanoKONTROL (4).

Secondly, finding a suitable printed circuit board (pcb) design software proved to be challenging. As the authors decided to use a custom made pcb to reduce noise in reading the potentiometers while facilitating construction and improving reliability, a pcb design software was needed. Due to licensing restrictions and costs, as well as no access to a Windows PC the authors were unable to use professional pcb design software (e.g. Eagle [12]) and decided to use Fritzing [13]. As a consequence the footprints of most of the parts used had to be designed manually as they weren't available in Fritzing's libraries. This process proved to be prone to errors and time consuming.

Thirdly, the specific nature of components create additional challenges as each design change means a redesign and re-manufacture of the pcb. For example, the micro USB-connector broke off from the cheap Arduino clone used in one of the prototypes after a few weeks, causing the authors to look for a different microcontroller. As the pin mapping differs from the various microcontroller types the board has to be redesigned¹. Something similar happened with the knobs. One prototype was designed prior deciding on a suitable knob for the potentiometers. After many weeks of online searching and shopping we settled on a knob which required a different orientation of the potentiometer on the pcb, forcing us to redesign the board again. As the validity of the hardware ultimately needed to be tested in real life, each hardware iteration had to be manufactured again, costing the authors money and time.

¹ Compare the pinout mapping of the Teensy 3.1. [1] with the Pro Micro [14].

3.2 Enclosure

Since the authors prioritised a comfortable layout of potentiometers over standardised dimensions for enclosures, ready-made industrial enclosures were not available. Further, customisation of said enclosures, i.e. drilling holes or engraving lattices for the potentiometers, through specialised companies would be prohibitive due to budget restrictions. Instead the authors opted for the DIY route here, too, using the tools and knowledge available to us, borrowing ideas found by other projects [15] [16]. This led the authors to base the design on a combination of slices of laser cut plywood and acrylic, as well as specially designed pcbs (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Corner view of the most recent version of the knobbox. The pcb serves as the face plate with the silkscreen and copper acting as labelling and markup. The frosted acrylic sheets envelope the plywood sheets to improve stiffness and design.

3.3 Budget

However, it is worth noting that some of these challenges could have been solved if a research budget would have been available for the development. A budget would have allowed the authors to hire knowledge and leverage access to professional manufacturing processes, including using CNC machines and laser cutters to process metals or injection moulds custom parts. Luckily, through help through our local Hackspace the authors found an affordable pcb manufacturing service freeing us from having to etch our own boards [17].

4. COMPROMISES AND OUTCOMES

The challenges in the design process and the specifics of the components lead to two controller types which differ in the way they solve the design requirements. One controller type uses a modular approach. Components are grouped on specialised, chainable boards which can be interconnected via cables (Figure 6). In the moment the authors created six different boards, each of them housing either the micro-controller and additional components, four 100 mm faders,

16 knobs, a pair of jack connectors for foot switches, an ethernet controller or 8 illuminated tactile switches. The other controller type uses a single pcb for all components.

Figure 6. Example of two chained knob based boards.

The modular approach suits the 100 mm faders well, facilitating the creation of fader boxes. As the pcb manufacture service the authors use offers the production of boards in quantities of five or ten, with ten boards costly almost the same as 5 boards, spreading repeating controls over several copies of the same board proved to be cost effective. For example, 16 faders of a faderbox could be spread over four boards each housing four faders. These four faders fit well on a board of 14 by 11 cm and the ten boards cost approximately 43 pounds with leaving 6 boards in spare. In comparison, attempting to fit the 16 faders on a single board would have either exceeded the service's maximum pcb dimensions or cost ineffective (ten boards of 14 by 30 cm would cost approximately 71 pounds, leaving 9 in spare). Chaining smaller boards together offers the side benefit that a controller can be customised to the number of controls the clients wishes. In the two prototypes built using this approach the authors chose a combination of faders and knobs which allow the hands to rest on the knobs. The layout of the faders is made to accommodate different playing techniques (Figure 7). However, due to the size of the faders and spacing, the 16 channel fader box exceeds the typical backpack size (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Illustration of the fader layout.

Figure 8. Size comparison between the 16 channel fader-box, nanoKONTROL and knobbox.

The single board solution suited the knobs well, leading to the creation of a knob box. As 9 mm knobs require a lot less space than 100 mm faders, a higher number of controls can be fitted on a small enough pcb, removing the need for chaining boards. However, in a single board situation the number of controls is not customisable per client anymore. In the moment, after a modular version, the authors settled on a pcb in the dimensions of approx. 24 cm by 15 cm, housing 32 knobs, 8 illuminated tactile switches, two jack sockets (expression pedal and MIDI out), as well as the microcontroller and additional circuitry (Figure 9, Figure 10). This made it possible to offer a high density of controls in a relatively compact way without having to sacrifice the layout and tactile feel of the controls while creating a device that is still backpack compatible. The layout of the potentiometers allows for adjusting adjacent potentiometers, prioritising the vertical over the horizontal (19 mm horizontally, 23 mm vertically). The knobs employed feature soft touch and round edges to improve tactile feel.

As may have become apparent, designing a controller also means finding a balance between competing criteria such as costs, type and number of controls, layout and portability. Each criteria may have different priority depending on the use scenario. In a sound diffusion context, large faders

Figure 9. Populated most-recent knobbox pcb.

Figure 10. Isometric view of the knobbox.

might be more useful as opposed to knobs, as around eight faders can be moved at once (4 per hand), instead of merely two knobs (1 per hand). A fader box for a diffusion system then would feature as many faders as possible and portability and costs (in terms of number of controls per space) might be less of an issue, compared with regard to the multiple reels of cables, stands and loudspeakers required to build a diffusion system. However in an electroacoustic improv context, portability and costs would be more important. Here knobs might be more useful, as they use less space and tend to be cheaper than large 100 mm faders, albeit smaller or fewer faders than knobs could be used.

Also, if a controller uses MIDI or OSC as a protocol equally depends on the priorities of the criteria or the use scenario. OSC via ethernet cables would require the use of a RJ-45 socket which in turn would require a lot of space, making a controller bulkier, especially when used in a combination with a readymade breakout board such as the Wiznet Wiz820io. Figure 11 illustrates how the RJ-45 socket would exceed the dimensions of the fader box. However, connecting a controller via ethernet would allow for scenarios where the computer is not in controller's proximity. Replacing ethernet with WIFI could solve the size issue, but WIFI hasn't been implemented, yet. In that sense, the authors decided to stay with MIDI purely for convenience, although the modular controller approach would support OSC if required.

Figure 11. Size comparison between the ethernet module (left) and the faderbox (right).

5. CONCLUSION

The paper discussed the challenges and solutions of a DIY approach in building mixer-style controllers which suit the performance of electroacoustic music better. The DIY route posed own challenges, such as budget restrictions limiting access to components, materials and production processes, as well as knowledge. As the Arduino platform provides Open Source libraries for communication and I/O management, the controller's software implementation proved to be less challenging than the hardware design. The authors made their controller firmware Open Source and opened unused microcontroller I/O's on the pcb, inviting customisation and extension by the user.

The paper also presented two types of controllers which resulted from different compromises in solving the design challenges – a fader box and a knob box. Both controllers aim at different aspect of the electroacoustic performance practise with one mainly meant for sound diffusion, the other one for the improvisation of electroacoustic music via knobs.

The authors currently focus on the development on the knob box. In a future revision, it will also allow boards to be chained while replacing the Arduino Pro Micro with a Teensy LC [18], improving customisation through more processing power and higher I/O count compared to the Arduino. Furthermore, an extension pcb featuring eight 80 mm faders will be offered, to augment the knob based approach through faders.

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6. REFERENCES

- [1] Korg, “nanoKONTROL2 SLIM-LINE USB CONTROLLER | MIDI Controllers | KORG,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.korg.com/us/products/controllers/nanokontrol2/>
- [2] Behringer, “Behringer: B-CONTROL FADER BCF2000,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.behringer.com/EN/Products/BCF2000.aspx>
- [3] LOUD Technologies Inc, “Mackie - Mackie Control Universal Pro,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.mackie.com/products/mcupro/>
- [4] J. E. Cobb, “An accelerometer based gestural capture system for performer based music composition,” 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/2252/>
- [5] A. R. Jensenius, R. Koehly, and M. M. Wanderley, “Building low-cost music controllers,” in *Computer Music Modeling and Retrieval*. Springer, 2006, pp. 123–129. [Online]. Available: http://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/11751069_11
- [6] R. Graham and B. Bridges, “Gesture and Embodied Metaphor in Spatial Music Performance Systems Design,” in *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression (2014)*. Goldsmiths University of London, 2014, pp. 581–584. [Online]. Available: http://nime2014.org/proceedings/papers/526_paper.pdf
- [7] PJRC, “Teensy 3.1: New Features,” 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pjrc.com/teensy/teensy31.html#specs>
- [8] Sparkfun Electronics, “Pro Micro - 5V/16MHz,” 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sparkfun.com/products/12640>
- [9] PJRC, “Teensyduino: Using USB Mouse with Teensy on the Arduino ID,” 2012. [Online]. Available: https://www.pjrc.com/teensy/td_midi.html
- [10] CNMAT, “OSC for Arduino and Embedded Processors,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://cnmat.berkeley.edu/oscuino>
- [11] Arduino LLC, “Arduino Playground - LibraryList,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://playground.arduino.cc/Main/LibraryList#Comm>
- [12] CadSoft, “Freeware | CadSoft EAGLE,” 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://www.cadsoftusa.com/download-eagle/freeware/>
- [13] IXDS, “Fritzing,” 2010. [Online]. Available: <http://fritzing.org/>
- [14] Jimb0, “Pro Micro & Fio v3 Hookup Guide,” 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://learn.sparkfun.com/tutorials/pro-micro--fio-v3-hookup-guide#hardware-overview-pro-micro>
- [15] SliceCase, “SliceCase,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.slicecase.com/about>
- [16] electrodacus, “Make a cool case out of PCB only,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.eevblog.com/forum/projects/make-a-cool-case-out-of-pcb-only/>
- [17] Elecrow, “10pcs- 2 layer PCB [SPP01010PP] - \$9.90: Elecrow bazaar, Make your making more easy,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.elecrow.com/10pcs-2-layer-pcb-p-1175.html>
- [18] PJRC, “Teensy LC (Low Cost),” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.pjrc.com/teensy/teensyLC.html>